

Development Of Social Competence Of Preschool Children On The Basis Of National Education

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Annotation. Knowledge instilled in the mind of a preschool child and spiritual values determine his future life due to mutual and family relations, caring for loved ones effective use of national educational methods and advanced achievements of modern pedagogues in children's education is important in forming a harmoniously developed child's personality

Keywords: preschool education, education, integration, educator, children, education, spiritual and moral education, methods of education

INTRODUCTION

Active teaching methods are methods that make it possible to activate the educational process and encourage the learner to participate creatively in it. The task of AMO is to ensure the development and self-development of the learner's personality based on identifying his or her individual characteristics and abilities, with a special place given to the development of theoretical thinking, which involves understanding the internal contradictions of the models being studied. Active teaching methods help develop learners' thinking; facilitate their involvement in solving problems that are as close as possible to professional ones; not only expand and deepen professional knowledge, but also develop practical skills and abilities.

Active teaching methods are divided into 2 types. Active teaching methods of the 1st type include problem-based lectures, problem-based practical classes and laboratory work, seminars and discussions, course and diploma projects, practice, internships, training and monitoring programs, conferences, olympiads, etc.

All of them are focused on the independent activity of the learner, problematic. But they do not imitate real circumstances in a conditional situation. Active teaching methods of the 2nd type (simulation) are divided into non-game and game. Non-game Active teaching methods include:

the method of analyzing specific situations, simulators, simulation exercises to find a known solution. Here there is modeling of real objects and situations, but there is no free play with role-playing functions. Game Active teaching methods include: business (management) games, the method of playing roles, individual game lessons on machine models. These methods are highly effective in the educational process and are used in leading educational institutions around the world. This method is close to the method of analyzing specific situations and the method of analyzing production situations.

Games can be imitation, organizational and activity, business. Organizational and activity games are used to solve complex social and production problems that require the combined efforts of various specialists. A business game (BG)

in its widespread, usual understanding is a method of simulating the adoption of management decisions in various production situations by playing according to given rules of a group of people or a person with a computer in a dialogue mode, aimed at creating in trainees the most complete feeling of real activity in the role of a decision maker.

Active learning methods can be used at various stages of the educational process:

Stage 1 – primary acquisition of knowledge. This can be a problem lecture, a heuristic conversation, an educational discussion, etc.

Stage 2 – knowledge control (reinforcement), methods such as collective thinking activity, testing, etc. can be used.

Stage 3 – formation of professional skills, abilities based on knowledge and development of creative abilities, it is possible to use modeled learning, game and non-game methods.

In the traditional organization of the educational process, a one-way form of communication is used as a way of transmitting information. Its essence lies in the transmission of information by the teacher and its subsequent reproduction by the student. The main source of learning is the experience of the teacher. The student is in a situation where he only reads, hears, speaks about certain areas of knowledge, occupying only the position of the perceiver. Sometimes one-sidedness can be violated (for example, when the student clarifies something or asks a question), and then two-way communication arises.

It is typical that the one-way form of communication is present not only in lectures, but also in seminars. The only difference is that it is not the teacher, but the student who transmits some information. This may be answers to questions posed by the teacher before the seminar, abstracts, or reproduction of lecture material. This form of communication, which has existed for such a long

time, is unacceptable today for many reasons. Let us name only some of the shortcomings of this method of teaching.

First of all, the passivity of the student during the lesson, his function is listening, while pedagogical and sociological studies show that very soon there is no trace left of passive participation in the learning process. There is a certain pattern of learning described by American researchers R. Karnikau and F. McElroe: a person remembers 10% of what he reads; 20% - heard; 30% of what he saw; 50% - seen and heard; 80% - what he says himself; 90% - what he achieved in the activity. The second reason is even simpler and more obvious: one-way communication is justified only in the case of a lack of information, the impossibility of obtaining it in any other way except from the lecturer's story. Today, in most cases, this is not the case. The teacher, as a rule, uses material that is not original. Only the methods of its construction, logic and manner of presentation are original. This is certainly valuable and testifies to the level and skill of the teacher, but it does little to help the student construct knowledge - someone else's construction of knowledge never becomes their own. You can admire it, but you still have to create your own.

A fundamentally different form of multilateral communication in the educational process. A specially organized method of multilateral communication presupposes the activity of each subject of the educational process, and not just the teacher, parity, the absence of repressive management and control measures on his part.

The number of intensive communicative contacts between the students themselves increases. Teaching, open in communicative terms, is characterized by the following statements:

1. Students learn better when they are allowed to approach the subject through their own experience.
2. Students learn better when the teacher actively supports their way of learning. This is possible

when there is a field between them and the subject of study that includes linguistic and non-linguistic activities.

3. Students perceive the material better when the teacher, on the one hand, structures the subject for easier learning, and on the other hand, accepts and includes in the discussion the opinions of students that do not coincide with his own point of view.

It should be noted that a multilateral form of communication not only allows one to abandon the monopoly on truth, but is also a necessary (but not sufficient) condition for the student to construct his/her knowledge.

Indeed, each participant in communication has the potential to, by meeting and colliding with the position of other participants, advance in the process of constructing knowledge (joint in form and individual in essence). Here, everyone builds their knowledge, for which they have a request today and which can be developed as the need arises - tomorrow or several years after graduation.

To implement the current requirements of today's education, new forms of training should be developed that will allow "to formulate doubts and gain experience in mastering controversy." It is advisable to conduct classes using interactive teaching methods that would force students to actively interact with the teacher and the audience.

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